

RESEARCH REPORT

DSM-III-R co-morbidity in benzodiazepine dependence

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Abstract

Aim, sample and measures. Co-morbidity has been shown to influence the clinical course of mental disorders. This paper describes DSM-III-R 1-month co-morbidity across axes I, II and III in a sample of 153 benzodiazepine dependants. All patients were evaluated through several in-depth clinical interviews across all five DSM-III-R axes. **Results.** Extensive co-morbidity existed across three DSM-III-R axes. All patients had at least one diagnosis in axis I; 81 (52.9%) in axis II and 50 (32.7%) in axis III. The most prevalent diagnoses were: insomnia, anxiety disorders and affective disorders in axis I; obsessive-compulsive, histrionic and dependent personality disorders in axis II and rheumatological, neurological and cardiovascular disorders in axis III. **Conclusions.** There were no cases of benzodiazepine dependence appearing alone. There were associations within and between axes, suggesting potential predisposing factors and a sequential model for benzodiazepine dependence is proposed. The findings reinforce the need for exhaustive diagnostic evaluation of patients prior to prescribing benzodiazepine.

Introduction

Benzodiazepines are one of the most commonly prescribed psychotropic drugs, with one of the widest ranges of indications.¹ Although they are among the safest drugs in clinical use some adverse reactions, such as dependence, do appear.

Various factors contribute to dependence: pharmacological characteristics (high affinity for the GABAergic receptor, short elimination half-life), high dosages and/or long-term use^{2,3} and

the simultaneous use of other substances, such as alcohol.^{2,4} However, the fact that not all long-term benzodiazepine users ultimately depend on them indicates that patient-related factors, such as age, presence of chronic illnesses and personality traits, may play a part in the development of dependence.^{2,5-7}

Co-morbidity is the diagnosis of more than one specific disorder in a person in a defined period of time.⁸ The terms co-morbidity and co-occurrence are used alternately, although per-

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haps one term ought to be used to mean "present at the same time" and another to mean "occurring in the same individual, whether contemporaneously or not". Following Andrews' suggestion, we have taken co-morbidity to mean the latter.⁹ Throughout various community studies, co-morbidity has been commonly found in patients with alcohol and other substance abuse disorders.^{10,11} The impact and implications in treatment and results have been studied increasingly in different psychiatric disorder,¹²⁻¹⁵ although the implications of somatic pathology have not yet been considered.

Many problems with drug and alcohol abuse start originally as ways of dealing with anxiety or depression. These mechanisms, as in other disorders (i.e. phobic avoidance, hysterical dissociation) lower painful experience symptoms, but may lead to maladaptation. In this sense, benzodiazepine dependence in some patients may be a maladaptive mechanism or a complication of previous anxiety or depressive disorders.¹⁶ Moreover, self-administration in multiple substance abusers may also lead to benzodiazepine dependence.¹⁷ Finally, when benzodiazepine dependence is the first disorder to appear, the others could be complications of withdrawal symptoms.¹⁸

Several in-depth studies have examined at benzodiazepine dependence. There are studies that describe the personality of these dependants by using specific scales.⁵ Others employ measures of stress implying the presence of psychiatric disorders.⁷ Finally, we have found studies which classify and analyse the psychiatric comorbidity associated with the long-term use of benzodiazepines, but without specifying whether the patients were dependant or not.^{6,19,20} However, these studies do not describe the clinical features of these dependants and, so far, there is no study that systematically analyses co-morbidity associated with benzodiazepine dependence.

This paper describes co-morbidity in axes I, II and III of DSM-III-R in a sample of benzodiazepine dependants and includes an analysis of the clinical implications.

Subject and methods

Recruitment procedure

The subjects in this study were 153 patients who between 1987 and 1991 were referred consecutively to a specialized unit for the treatment of

benzodiazepine dependence. The unit caters for one National Health Service area in Madrid, covering 417 000 inhabitants. All patients completed initial evaluation and subsequent follow-up.

Benzodiazepine use

A detailed description of benzodiazepines and their use in our sample has already been reported.³

The average duration of benzodiazepine use was 4.64 years (SD = 3.89); 37.6% of the patients had been taking benzodiazepines for more than 5 years, 30.5% for 1-3 years and 24.8% for 3-5 years. Only 7.1% of all patients had been taking benzodiazepines for less than a year. In almost half the cases ($N = 85$, 47.8%), benzodiazepines were initially taken only at night. Of these, 24 (13.5% of the total) started to take the same benzodiazepine during the day as well. Clarification of the diagnosis that motivated the prescription was not reliable due to the long period of use.

Forty-nine prescriptions (27.5%) were considered to be "hypnotic drugs" and the other 129 "anxiolytic" by the laboratories which market them, although this consideration did not always coincide with the use given to them. All patients took the drugs on a regular basis.

Procedure

Information was obtained during clinical interviews with the patient and relatives or other relevant people (not less than six 1-hour interviews with each patient). All interviews were carried out by the main researcher (H.M.C.), a psychiatrist with wide clinical experience in dependencies and the use of DSM-III-R. Each patient was evaluated to establish a cross-sectional, 1-month prevalence of any particular disorder in all five DSM-III-R axes. Together with the diagnosis of benzodiazepine dependence, a principal diagnosis plus any additional diagnoses was made, following the recommendations of the DSM-III-R.²¹ In the case of axis III, the diagnoses of etiological value and those involving an emotional impact on the patient were included.

For axis II, efforts were made to obtain a single diagnosis to avoid the overlapping demonstrated by some authors.¹³ Patients who simultaneously fulfilled the criteria for two or more

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the sample

	N (%) Male	N (%) Female
Sex	55 (35.9)	98 (64.1)
Age		
Mean (SD) (NS)	45.2 (15.84)	47.86 (13.89)
Age distribution (NS)		
20-35	19 (34.5)	19 (19.4)
36-50	14 (25.5)	37 (37.7)
51-65	14 (25.5)	26 (26.5)
> 65	8 (14.5)	16 (16.3)
Education (NS)		
Less than high school	34 (61.8)	73 (74.5)
High school graduated without a college degree	11 (20)	18 (18.4)
College graduated	10 (18.2)	7 (7.1)
Marital status ^{*a}		
Never married	19 (34.5)	16 (16.3)
Married	34 (61.8)	58 (59.2)
Widowed ^{*b}	1 (1.8)	16 (16.3)
Separated/Divorced	1 (1.8)	8 (8.2)
Employment ^{*c}		
Currently employed	26 (47.3)	26 (26.5)
Housewives ^{*c}	0	54 (55.1)
Retired	17 (30.9)	11 (11.2)
Not employed	12 (21.8)	7 (7.2)

^{*a} $p < 0.005$; ^{*b} $p < 0.05$; ^{*c} $p < 0.00001$.

personality disorders (PDs) were assigned a "personality disorder not elsewhere specified" diagnosis. Personality traits were not taken into account so as to avoid large overlap.

Statistical analysis

Differences between the sexes were calculated using the χ^2 test for qualitative and *t*-test for quantitative variables. When the expected number of cases in a cell of a 2×2 table was less than 5, Fisher's test was used. The significance level was established at $p < 0.05$.

Co-morbidity associations of axes I, II and III were examined by calculating odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) (10).

Exact confidence intervals were calculated following the Mehta *et al.* method.²² Prior to that, the MacNemar test was used for paired results to evaluate the association between the different axes.²³

Results

General characteristics of the patients

The sample consisted of 55 men (35.9%) and 98 women (64.1%). Their average age was 45.2 (15.84) and 47.86 (13.89) years, respectively.

The age distribution revealed no significant differences between the sexes. The majority of our patients ($N = 92$, 60%) were married. We found a significant difference between the sexes in terms of marital status ($p < 0.005$), with a higher presence of widowed women than men ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1).

Most patients ($N = 107$, 69.9%) had no high school education and in this respect there was no difference between the sexes. Working status was significantly different, with the majority of women (55.1%) being housewives ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1).

Overall distribution by diagnosis

A statistical association was found between diagnoses in axes I and II and diagnoses in axes I and III ($p < 0.001$); 31 patients had diagnoses in all three axes. Finally, a statistically significant association existed between having a diagnosis in both axes II and III ($p < 0.01$).

Axis I diagnoses

The principal diagnosis of 117 patients (76.47%) was in axis I. The largest proportion ($N = 39$) suffered from anxiety disorders, the next most

Table 2. DSM-III-R axis I, II and III diagnoses in 153 patients with benzodiazepine dependence

	Total (patients) N	Principal ¹ (no. dx.) (%)	Additional ¹ (no. dx.) (%)
Axis I* ^a	153	76.47	67.32
Insomnia* ^a	54	38.89	75.92
Anxiety disorders	47	82.98	17.02
Affective disorders* ^a	31	74.19	29.03
Substance use / abstinence disorders* ^a	30	30	100
Alcohol	24	4.2	95.8
Stimulants	5	40	60
Opiates	3	66.7	33.3
Sedatives	2	—	100
Other	6	66.7	33.3
Somatoform disorders	20	90	10
Psychotic disorders	6	66.67	33.33
Other* ^a	14	35.71	78.57
Axis II	81	24.69	75.31
Cluster A	1	100	0
Schizoid PD	1	100	0
Cluster B	26	26.92	73.08
Histrionic PD	17	11.76	88.24
Borderline PD	5	60	40
Antisocial PD	3	33.33	66.67
Narcissistic PD	1	100	0
Cluster C	48	22.92	77.08
Obsessive-compulsive PD	34	29.41	70.59
Dependent PD	13	7.69	92.31
Avoidant PD	1	0	100
Not specified PD	6	16.67	83.33
Axis III* ^a	53	22.64	100
Rheumatological	23	0	100
Neurological* ^a	18	27.78	77.78
Cardiovascular* ^a	10	30	80
Gastrointestinal	2	0	100
Other* ^a	13	30.77	100

*^aMultiple diagnoses in some patients. ¹Principal and additional diagnoses were made in axis I and II according to DSM-III-R criteria. Although principal diagnoses are restricted to axis I and II according to DSM-III-R criteria, we have presented in this table those axis III diagnoses with etiologic value as "Principal diagnoses", and those with some emotional impact in the patient as "Additional diagnoses".

prevalent diagnosis being affective and sleep disorders (23 and 21, respectively) (Table 2).

Seventy-eight patients had at least one additional diagnosis in axis I, independent of the principal diagnosis in any of the three axes. Of these patients, 37 had sleep disorders and 23 substance abuse/withdrawal disorders. Other additional diagnoses in axis I were affective and anxiety disorders (Table 2).

Anxiety disorders. In this class, four individual diagnoses were found: panic attacks with/without agoraphobia, generalized anxiety disorder, ob-

sessive-compulsive disorder and social phobia. The most frequent of these diagnoses was panic attacks with/without agoraphobia, followed by generalized anxiety disorder.

A significant association was noted between anxiety disorders and insomnia (OR = 3.44; 95% CI 1.29–9.18) and substance use disorders (3.15; 1.11–8.3) in axis I (Table 3). In axis II, anxiety disorders appeared significantly associated with cluster "C" PDs (3.98; 1.2–13.22) (Table 4). Finally, cardiovascular disorders were strongly associated with anxiety disorders (7.07; 1.57–31.86) (Table 3).

Table 3. Co-occurrence of 1-month prevalent DSM-III-R axis I with axis I and axis III disorders in 153 patients with benzodiazepine dependence

Axis I disorders	Axis I disorders							Axis III disorders*			
	Insomnia	Anxiety disorders	Affective disorders	Substance use disorders	Somatiform disorders	Axis III	Rheumatological disorders	Neurological disorders	Cardiovascular disorders		
Insomnia	—	—	—	—	—	2.9 [1.35-6.23]	8.55 [2.35-31.06]	0.62 [0.19-1.99]	0.9 [0.23-3.62]		
Anxiety disorders	3.44 [1.29-9.18]	—	—	—	—	0.6 [0.26-1.34]	0.42 [0.11-1.61]	0.73 [0.19-2.82]	7.07 [1.57-31.86]		
Affective disorders	17.53 [5.7-53.88]	1.7 [0.31-4.43]	—	—	—	0.74 [0.29-1.78]	0.74 [0.18-3.02]	3.5 [0.83-14.7]	—		
Substance use disorders	1.32 [0.5-3.48]	3.15 [1.11-8.3]	1.73 [0.57-5.27]	—	—	—	—	—	—		
Somatiform disorders	—	—	—	—	—	1.84 [0.62-5.28]	1.54 [0.36-6.67]	—	—		
Psychotic disorders	5.52 [0.88-34.48]	—	—	7.96 [1.26-50.29]	—	—	—	—	—		

This table presents odds ratio (OR) and [95% confidence interval] for every combination. When the number of patients for a cell was 3 or less, OR was not displayed.

*Data regarding gastrointestinal disorders in axis III were not presented, because all cells were empty.

Table 4. Co-occurrence of 1-month prevalent DSM-III-R axis II with axis I and axis III disorders in 153 patients with benzodiazepine dependence

Axis II disorders	Axis I disorders*						Axis III disorders**			
	Insomnia	Anxiety disorders	Affective disorders	Substance use disorders	Somatiform disorders	Axis III	Rheumatological disorders	Neurological disorders	Cardiovascular Disorders	
Cluster "A"	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
Cluster "B"	—	0.41 [0.12-1.36]	0.63 [0.2-1.99]	22.71 [4.55-113.5]	28.59 [3.4-242.2]	0.43 [0.12-1.3]	—	—	—	
Histrionic PD	—	0.55 [0.14-2.14]	0.34 [0.07-1.64]	1.66 [0.45-6.15]	—	0.83 [0.22-2.74]	—	—	—	
Borderline PD	—	0.7 [0.07-6.64]	5.21 [0.8-33.74]	26.4 [2.67-260.7]	28.59 [3.4-242.2]	—	—	—	—	
Antisocial PD	—	—	—	OR = Infinite <i>p</i> = 0.004	—	—	—	—	—	
Cluster "C"	7.2 [2.57-21.83]	3.98 [1.2-13.22]	1.04 [0.37-2.92]	—	0.06 [0.01-0.47]	3.48 [1.58-7.62]	2.3 [0.83-6.25]	1.9 [0.6-5.78]	1.63 [0.38-6.33]	
Obsessive-compulsive PD	15.87 [5.25-48.02]	1.77 [0.65-4.82]	0.51 [0.17-1.49]	—	0.13 [0.01-1.03]	2.61 [1.1-6.12]	3.4 [1.17-9.49]	1.41 [0.36-4.64]	1.18 [0.19-5.12]	
Dependent PD	0.23 [0.05-1.12]	2.03 [0.58-7.09]	3.31 [0.96-11.4]	—	—	3.73 [1.00-15.25]	1.8 [0.29-7.81]	2.5 [0.39-11.2]	—	

This table presents odds ratio (OR) and [95% confidence interval] for every combination. When the number of patients for a cell was 3 or less, OR was not displayed.
 *Data regarding psychotic disorders in axis I were not presented, because all cells were empty. **Data regarding gastrointestinal disorders in axis III were not presented, because all cells were empty.

Affective disorders. Dysthymia was the most frequent diagnosis in this class ($N=26$). Other diagnoses were atypical depression, major depression and bipolar disorder, with one case of each.

There was extensive interaction between dysthymia and insomnia in axis I (17.53; 5.7–53.88) (Table 3). Other diagnoses that coincided were anxiety and substance use disorders in axis I, cluster "C" PDs in axis II and, once again, a high prevalence of axis III diagnoses.

Sleep disorders. Non-organic insomnia was the most frequent diagnosis, whether principal or additional ($N=43$). The next most frequent sleep disorder was organic insomnia ($N=18$). There was one case of primary insomnia.

As mentioned above, a statistical association was found between insomnia (of all kinds) and affective and anxiety disorders in axis I (Table 3). Insomnia appeared in association with cluster "C" PDs in axis II (7.2; 2.57–21.83) and, in particular, with obsessive-compulsive PDs (15.87; 5.25–48.02) (Table 4). A significant association was also noted between insomnia and rheumatological disorders (8.55; 2.35–31.06) and, in general, with axis III diagnoses (2.9; 1.35–6.23) (Table 3).

Somatoform disorders. Hypochondriasis, conversion hysteria, somatization disorder and psychogenic pain were the individual diagnoses in this section, conversion hysteria being the most frequent. Comorbidity of somatoform disorders with axis I diagnoses was scarce (Table 3). In the case of axis II, a very significant association was found with cluster "B" P.D.s (28.59; 3.4–242.2), specifically border-line P.D. (28.59; 3.4–242.2) (Table 4). In contrast, the existence of cluster "C" P.D.s protected the patient from suffering from somatoform disorders (0.06; 0.01–0.47). Eleven patients had an additional diagnosis in axis III, rheumatologic disorders being the most frequent. No statistical association was found with this axis.

Substance use/withdrawal disorders. These diagnoses, either principal or additional, were given to 30 patients. However, 39 diagnoses were made confirming multiple drug use in eight patients (26.7%). These patients had other additional DSM-III-R diagnoses, reflecting the high

co-morbidity of these disorders. A striking association was found with cluster "B" PDs (22.71; 4.55–113.5). Indeed, both borderline (26.4; 2.67–260.7) and antisocial PDs ($OR = \infty$ ($p = 0.004$)) were strongly associated with substance use disorders (Table 4). A significant association was also found with psychotic disorders in axis I (see next section). The low prevalence of axis III co-morbid diagnoses (causing an emotional impact) within this category was surprising, although all patients had at least one diagnosis (with no emotional impact) in this axis.

Psychotic disorders. Psychotic disorders were strongly associated with substance use disorders (7.96; 1.26–50.29) (Table 3). No diagnoses were made in axes II or III.

Axis II diagnoses

The principal diagnosis of 20 patients was in axis II (Table 2). Numerous additional diagnoses were recorded in axis II, together with a principal diagnosis in other axes. Cluster "B" ($N=26$) and cluster "C" ($N=48$) PDs were much more prevalent than cluster "A" PDs ($N=1$). Within these cluster groups, the following PDs were the most prevalent: obsessive-compulsive ($N=34$), histrionic ($N=17$), dependent ($N=13$), border-line ($N=5$) and antisocial ($N=3$) (Table 2).

With regard to co-morbidity in axis II diagnoses, we found a significant association between cluster "C" PDs and axis III diagnoses (3.48; 1.58–7.62). Consequently, dependent PDs appeared to be associated with axis III diagnoses (3.73; 1.00–15.25) and obsessive-compulsive PDs with rheumatological disorders (3.4; 1.17–9.49) and axis III disorders in general (2.61; 1.1–6.12) (Table 4). Cluster "A" and "B" diagnoses in axis III were scarce (see above for data on axes I and II).

Axis III diagnoses

Fifty patients were given axis III diagnoses (in 12 of them it was of aetiological value), with rheumatological ($N=23$), neurological ($N=18$) and cardiovascular ($N=10$) being the most prevalent. Co-morbidity with axes I and II has already been mentioned (Tables 3 and 4).

Discussion

This is the first systematic study to report on the simultaneous DSM-III-R diagnoses of benzodiazepine dependants. These results are limited because of the cross-sectional survey in which no standardized interview format was used. However, this approach was based on several considerations. Unfortunately, when the data were collated, there was no standardized interview format to cover the full spectrum of psychiatric disorders, particularly sleep disorders (one of the main reasons for prescribing benzodiazepines). We tried to overcome this limitation by increasing clinical observation. In addition, clinical interviews throughout the follow-up period helped to make a more accurate diagnosis. In this sense, it has been claimed that the diagnosis of most PDs is better obtained through longitudinal clinical observation than through a single structured interview.²⁴

There was high co-morbidity across all three DSM-III-R axes in our sample, demonstrating a high level of psychopathology. The vast majority of the diagnoses assigned to each patient corresponded with diagnoses that occurred simultaneously at the initial evaluation and, due to the retrospective nature of the assessment, it was difficult to establish their order of appearance reliably. However, the fact that PDs appeared to be associated with sleep, anxiety, affective and substance abuse disorders, respectively, could mean that PDs may trigger other disorders, in which case co-morbidity would be sequential. This mechanism has already been demonstrated in anxiety and depressive disorders.⁹ A minority of co-morbid diagnoses in axis I followed benzodiazepine dependence, resulting in a complication of withdrawal symptoms.

With regard to analysis of the various diagnoses, the most prevalent one in axis I was insomnia. The existence of primary insomnia was scarce, thus not confirming the high prevalence figures reported in some studies.²⁵ However, insomniacs presented a high prevalence of psychopathology, which is consistent with other studies.²⁶ Some studies have shown that insomniacs tend to overestimate the efficacy of benzodiazepines, forgetting about their sleepless periods at night once under medication.²⁷ This powerful motive not to stop benzodiazepine use could be a contributing factor to dependence.

The association between insomnia and affective

disorders has already been established.²⁶ These patients, although clinically depressed, maintained that they did not feel depressed but were worried about their inability to sleep. In these cases, the risk of dependence could be increased if benzodiazepines are prescribed without antidepressants.

The prevalence of obsessive-compulsive PDs in the cases of insomnia was striking. This association was first hypothesized by Kalcs *et al.*, who proposed the internalization of emotions and an increase in secondary arousal as causing insomnia.²⁸ A psychotherapeutic approach to treatment is made harder by the patients' controller and normative traits, thus contributing to benzodiazepine dependence.

Finally, there was a high co-occurrence of insomnia and axis III diagnoses, in particular rheumatological disorders. This association can be explained by the fact that insomnia often develops in patients whose medical disorders cause pain, physical discomfort, anxiety and/or depression.²⁹

Anxiety disorders were the second most prevalent diagnosis in axis I. In this category, there was a significant association with insomnia (see above) and substance abuse disorders in axis I, cluster "C" diagnoses in axis II and cardiovascular disorders in axis III. The high prevalence and the implications of anxiety symptoms among alcoholics has been reviewed by Schuckit & Hesselbrock.³⁰ However, it is not clear from the literature available whether the high rate of anxiety disorders appears only within the context of heavy drinking and/or withdrawal or whether it indicates an underlying, life-long anxiety disorder. In these cases, if anxiety symptoms are temporary and appear only within this context, long-term treatment with benzodiazepines is to be avoided owing to the risk of developing dependence. These results confirmed those presented in recent literature which demonstrate that the presence of panic disorders is highly associated with substance abuse and dependence.^{10,11} A life-long risk for substance use disorders above 40%, particularly sedative abuse has been reported.³¹

The relationship between anxiety and anancastic and dependent PDs has already been established.³² Personality is one of the predisposing factors that influences the individual's response to psychological trauma and determines the form the anxiety disorder will take. Furthermore, the

handicapping influence of PDs can also be responsible for dependence.

Finally, we found a marked association between anxiety and cardiovascular disorders in axis III, as reported previously in the literature.³³ Benzodiazepine dependence could be regarded as a complication in the long-term treatment of the common symptoms of anxiety and cardiovascular disorders, due to their chronic nature.

The third most frequent co-morbid diagnosis in axis I was affective disorders, mainly dysthymia. Apart from insomnia, we also found other co-morbid diagnoses. Longitudinal studies have revealed a worse course for nearly all depressive syndromes among individuals with co-morbidity.³⁴

In the case of most substance abusers, benzodiazepines were used to reduce the undesirable effects of the main drug. For example, alcoholics took them to relieve their discomfort. This discomfort may have been due to a prolonged state of withdrawal, or to the social and psychological trauma associated with chronic alcoholism. A previous dysphoric state may predispose a person to alcoholism. The mechanism of the various subjective states at the receptor level may be that the GABA system is altered in alcoholics, either as a result of chronic drinking or as a predisposing factor prior to the drinking problem.³⁵

In cocaine dependants, the disinhibiting effect of benzodiazepines alleviated the "crash" period, also contributing to a reduction in excitation and insomnia, secondary to cocaine intoxication. In heroin abusers, benzodiazepines promoted sleepiness, particularly when they had run out of opiates. With regard to co-morbidity, there was a high presence of "impulsive" personalities (histrionic, borderline and antisocial) among substance abusers. These findings confirm those of the ECA and NCS studies.^{10,11} The abuse of and subsequent dependence on benzodiazepines would constitute one step further in the substance abuse escalation. The significance of this association remains unknown; various hypotheses have been put forward, ranging from a common aetiology for both personality and drug use disorders to treating them as one secondary to the other.³⁶ This co-morbidity results in poor therapeutic response and contributes indirectly to the development of benzodiazepine dependence.

We found a strong association between somatization and "dramatic" PDs. This finding

confirms those traditionally related to hysteria (conversion disorder)³⁷ and hypochondriasis.³⁸ This co-occurrence makes a therapeutic approach harder and the use of psychotropic drugs alone to alleviate the symptoms could result in dependence.

We observed some cases of alcoholism and caffeine abuse/dependence among the schizophrenics in our sample. These patients constituted a high-risk segment of the population for substance abuse.^{10,11,39} There are two hypotheses to explain this finding. First, the disease is provoked by alcohol abuse in a vulnerable population. Secondly, substance abuse reflects the patient's self-medication to control some of the non-productive schizophrenic symptoms or to ameliorate or neutralize the adverse effects of neuroleptics.³⁹

Finally, benzodiazepine dependence among schizophrenics reflected its prescription to minimize the adverse effects of neuroleptics. However, due to their partial antipsychotic activity,^{1,40} it may attenuate the symptomatology, thus delaying the diagnosis and correct treatment of schizophrenia. The persistence of symptomatology and its treatment with benzodiazepines for long periods would increase the risk of dependence.

Two types of PDs were highly prevalent in our study. The first was borderline PD, characterized by unstable mood and impulsive behaviour. Any form of mental distress leads to a demand for immediate gratification. These patients would prefer abusing higher doses of short elimination half-life, high potency benzodiazepines, with rapid oral absorption, in their search for a rapid effect.^{41,42} The second type was the timid worrier, highly susceptible to punishment, tender-minded and socially compliant, included in cluster "C" of the DSM-III-R. These personalities constitute a large proportion of anxious patients who are often described as suffering from "chronic anxiety". Their preferred drugs are benzodiazepines, usually taken in low doses over long periods and with little or no effect on the underlying disease. Moreover, these patients have more withdrawal symptoms than other long-term benzodiazepine users.^{41,42}

With regard to the relationship between axis II and axis III, we found a marked association between somatic diseases with chronic pain (particularly rheumatological disorders) and obsessive-compulsive PD (Table 4). Apprehension is

very noticeable in these patients. All pain with a chronic course worries them, amplifying pain perception.⁴³ Benzodiazepines are partially effective because they reduce apprehension. However, the chronic nature of most diseases with associated pain and the fact that most treatments are palliative tends to prolong the persistent administration of benzodiazepines and their subsequent dependence.

Conclusions

In our sample benzodiazepine dependence never occurred in isolation but was associated with other disorders in any of the three DSM-III-R axes. In some cases, these disorders may have triggered benzodiazepine dependence. Before prescribing a benzodiazepine clinicians must carefully evaluate the patient's psychiatric status and its consequent effect on risk of dependency.

In addition, daily maintenance treatment must also be established on a case-by-case basis and should be regularly re-evaluated in order to ensure that continued benzodiazepine use is therapeutic and justified.

Finally, in most cases dependence occurs at doses within the therapeutic range. These data indicate that giving consideration only to non-medical use, as did NCS, could constitute a selection bias when analysing abuse and dependence.⁴⁴

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